

Fig. 1. Plots of $k_{\text{obs}}(K_a + [H^+])/[H^+]$ vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ for Ni^{II} -L-arginine interaction at different temperatures.

with L- α -amino- δ -guanidinovaleric acid is much faster than that of Ni^{II} . This can be explained on the basis of difference in CFSE (Oh-TBP) values⁷. The lower value in the case of Cu^{II} is responsible for the higher value of k_0 . This is further supported by lower values of enthalpies of activation for the Cu^{II} complex (Table 1). The values of specific rate constants k_{12} and k_{43} indicate that in both cases, the zwitterionic form is more reactive than the diprotonated form at all temperatures. This is further supported by the corresponding activation parameter values. High negative values of entropy of activation are suggestive of the associative mechanism being followed.

Experimental

L- α -Amino- δ -guanidinovaleric acid (Sisco), $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (both Merck), 2,6-lutidine (Merck-Schuchardt), bromothymol blue (B.D.H.), KNO_3 ,

KOH and HNO_3 (all A.R. grade) were used as obtained. Triple-distilled water was used for the preparation of all solutions.

Methods: The kinetic study was made using an Aminco-Morrow stopped-flow spectrophotometer as described earlier¹⁰. The complexation reactions with Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were investigated in the pH range 5.9–7.1 and 2.2–3.2 respectively, at an ionic strength of 0.1 M KNO_3 and at 25–40° ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) under pseudo-first order condition by taking large excess of metal ion over the ligand. Oscilloscope traces of voltage versus time were used to determine the values of pseudo-first order rate constants and these were further utilised to evaluate the values of second order rate constants. Blank experiments showed no kinetic effects.

References

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